

Synthesis and structural characterization of an ion-pair complex [Zn(tp)][Zn(NCS)₄] [tp = tetraethylenepentamine]

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Abstract : Reaction of appropriate molar ratios of Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O, tp and NH₄SCN in aqueous methanol at room temperature affords an ion-pair complex [Zn(tp)][Zn(NCS)₄] (1) [tp = tetraethylenepentamine] which has been characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic and other physicochemical results. X-Ray structural analysis reveals that in 1, the zinc(II) ion has a distorted trigonal bipyramidal environment in the cationic part coordinated through five N atoms of tp and the molecular anion has a distorted tetrahedral geometry with a ZnN₄ environment. In the crystalline state multiple N-H···S hydrogen bonds coupled with S···S interactions resulted in a 3D network structure. The compound shows thermal stability up to 270 °C.

Keywords : Zinc(II) tetrathiocyanatometallate, tetraethylenepentamine, synthesis, X-ray structure.

Introduction

The chemistry of tetrathiocyanatometallates like [M^{II}(NCS)₄]²⁻ (M = Co, Cu, Zn), [Mn(NCS)₄(H₂O)₂]²⁻ and [Hg(SCN)₄]²⁻ as multiple connectors in bi- and polymeric complexes¹⁻⁹ or as anionic counterpart in ion-pair complexes¹⁰⁻¹³ are well documented. In combination with different metal-ligand templates like [M^{II}(L)_n]²⁺ (M' = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn; L = neutral ligand) as cationic counter parts, these tetrathiocyanatometallates are very much useful for the isolation of complexes with different dimensionalities through covalent bonds specially, -M'-NCS-M- bridge and/or multiple non-covalent interactions such as hydrogen bondings^{14,15} and S···S interactions^{12,16} etc. Earlier we reported^{10,12,13} some ion-pair complexes of the types [Zn(L)][Zn(NCS)₄], (dpaH)₂[Hg(SCN)₄], [Zn(tren)(NCS)]₂[Cu(NCS)₄] and [Zn(tren)(NCS)]₂[Zn(NCS)₄] [dpaH = protonated 2,2'-dipyridylamine; L = N-(1-pyridin-2-ylformylidene)-N'-[2-{2-[(1-pyridin-2-ylformylidene)amino]ethyl}amino)ethyl]ethane-1,2-diamine; tren = tris(2-aminoethyl)amine]. In the present endeavour, we have examined the reaction behaviour between tetrathiocyanatozincate(II), [Zn(NCS)₄]²⁻ in combination with the complementary unit [Zn(tp)]²⁺ [tp = tetraethylenepentamine]. Successfully, we have isolated an ion-pair complex [Zn(tp)][Zn(NCS)₄] (1). The

details of synthesis, spectroscopic studies and structure of 1 are described below.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

Compound 1 was obtained by reaction of [Zn(tp)]²⁺ with [Zn(NCS)₄]²⁻ in aqueous-methanol (see Experimental) at room temperature. It is sufficiently stable in open atmosphere. Analytical data for the compound are consistent with the calculated value. 1 is moderately soluble in a range of common organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide and the solubility increases on warming. In MeCN solution, 1 shows lower conductivity value (95 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) than that expected for 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour¹⁷ reflecting molecular association of the complex ions.

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectrum of 1, ν(N-H) stretching frequencies of the -NH₂ group¹³ of tp are seen at 3292 cm⁻¹ and 3241 cm⁻¹. Several weak bands in the range 2970-2910 cm⁻¹ assignable to aliphatic C-H stretching vibration are routinely observed. Strong bands at 2098 and 2085 cm⁻¹ are invariably seen attributed to the ν(NCS) stretching¹⁸ mode of the molecular anion; such multiple bands are in the

line with different force constants of the thiocyanates which is presumably due to engagement of the thiocyanates in different types of hydrogen bondings with the amine hydrogens in the crystalline state. A band corresponding to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ stretching frequency¹⁸ appears at 743 cm^{-1} . In MeCN solution, **1** displays absorption band at 271 nm presumably due to ligand origin¹⁹.

Thermal analysis :

To examine the thermal stability of the compound, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were made between $30\text{--}800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a static atmosphere of nitrogen. The TG curve (Fig. S1) shows that compound **1** is stable up to $270\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and then gradual decomposition takes place in two successive steps between the temperature range $270\text{--}700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (weight loss : observed, 71.07% and calculated, 76.31%) corresponding to four thiocyanates and one tp ligand. The final product corresponds to two equivalent of zinc oxide moieties as appeared from the calculation of the residual mass percentage (weight : observed, 27.58% and calculated, 29.46%) as well as colour change from yellow to white when hot and when cold, respectively.

Fig. S1. Thermal decomposition behaviour of **1**.

Crystal structure :

Structural analysis reveals that asymmetric unit in **1** consists of discrete $[\text{Zn}(\text{tp})]^{2+}$ dication and $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ dianion which are connected to each other through $\text{N}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{S}$ hydrogen bonds and weak cooperative $\text{S}\cdots\text{S}$ inter-

actions affording a 3D network structure. An ORTEP diagram of the asymmetric unit and perspective view of the 3D network are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Selected bond distances and angles relevant to the coordination spheres of the metal(II) center in the asymmetric unit are set in Table 1.

In the cationic part of **1** zinc(II) center adopts a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry as exemplified by the τ^{20} parameter [$\tau = 0.55$ ($\text{Zn}2$)] with a ZnN_5 chromophore (Fig. 1). Two primary amine N atoms (N5 and N9) and one secondary amine N atom (N7) of tp define the equatorial positions whereas remaining two secondary amine N atoms (N6 and N8) occupy the axial sites. Zn2 deviates slightly (0.065 \AA) from the mean equatorial plane containing three N atoms of tp. Zn2-N(equatorial) distances [$2.016(10)\text{--}2.073(10)\text{ \AA}$] are somewhat shorter than Zn2-N(axial) bond lengths [$2.167(11)\text{--}2.169(11)\text{ \AA}$] as expected¹³. The coordination environment around the zinc(II) center in $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ is best described as distorted tetrahedron with ZnN_4 chromophore coordinated by four N atoms of the terminal thiocyanate ligands

(Fig. 2). The Zn-N bond lengths lie within a close range of $1.944(11)\text{--}1.957(12)\text{ \AA}$ (Table 1) similar to that found in literature^{10,13}. The average tetrahedral N-Zn-N bond angles (Table 1) around each metal(II) center in $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ unit are close to ideal value (109.50°).

Fig. 1. An ORTEP view of the asymmetric unit in **1** with atom labeling schemes and 50% thermal ellipsoid probability for all non-hydrogen atoms.

In crystalline state, tetrahedral $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ units in **1** act as a template of the N–H \cdots S hydrogen bonded network by organizing pentacoordinated $[\text{Zn}(\text{tp})]^{2+}$ moieties into a 3D supramolecular architecture (Fig. 2). Zn1 tetrahedra are connected through weak cooperative S \cdots S interactions^{12,16,21} (S3 \cdots S4 : 3.755 Å; Symmetry code : $1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1-z$) affording columnar assemblies along the crystallographic *a*-axis (Fig. 2b). In this network, tetrahedral Zn1 and trigonal bipyramidal Zn2 centers are placed alternatively (Fig. 2a) and connected through multiple weak N–H \cdots S hydrogen bondings (N5–H1 \cdots S3ⁱ : 2.81 Å, 159°; N6–H7 \cdots S3ⁱⁱ : 2.66 Å, 171°; N8–H17 \cdots S4ⁱⁱⁱ : 2.83 Å, 145°; N9–H22 \cdots S2^{iv} : 2.64 Å, 173°; N9–H23 \cdots S4^v : 2.60 Å, 156°; Symmetry codes : *i* = $1-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; *ii* = $-1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1-z$; *iii* = $-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; *iv* = $x, -1+y, -1+z$; *v* = $x, y, -1+z$). Three uncoordinated S atoms (S2, S3 and S4) of $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ and –NH₂ (H1, H22 and H22)/–NH– (H7 and H17) hydrogen atoms of $[\text{Zn}(\text{tp})]^{2+}$ moiety play important roles in such type of hydrogen bondings towards formation of the 3D network structure (Fig. 2). The shortest internuclear Zn1 \cdots Zn1 and Zn1 \cdots Zn2 separations are 8.229 Å and 6.425 Å, respectively.

Conclusion :

The use of molecular anion $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ in concert with $[\text{Zn}(\text{tp})]^{2+}$ containing bifunctional ligands^{13,22} with metal ion binding centers as well as hydrogen bond donor/acceptor sites leads to successful isolation of a new ion-pair complex **1** which is X-ray crystallographically characterized. In crystalline states, multiple N–H \cdots S hydrogen bonds among the cationic and anionic units coupled with weak cooperative S \cdots S interactions between the molecular anions $[\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ lead to a 3D network.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (Fluka, Germany), tetraethylenepentamine (Fluka, Germany) and ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. Zinc(II) perchlorate hexahydrates were prepared¹³ by treatment of their respective carbonates with perchloric acid (E. Merck, India) followed by slow evaporation on a steam-bath, filtration through a fine glass-frit, and preserved in a desiccator containing concentrated sulfuric acid (E. Merck,

Fig. 2. Perspective views of 3D network structure in **1** formed through N–H...S hydrogen bonds and S...S interactions.

India) for subsequent uses. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solution, and dry MeCN was used as solvent. UV-Vis (in MeCN) spectrum was recorded with a Jasco model V-570 UV-Vis-NIR spec-

trophotometer. Thermal behaviour was investigated with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer with samples heated from 30–800 °C under nitrogen.

Synthesis of [Zn(tp)][Zn(NCS)₄] (1) :

A colourless methanolic solution (10 ml) of Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.372 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of NH₄NCS (304 mg, 4 mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml). In an another container Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.372 g, 1 mmol) and tp (0.189 g, 1 mmol) were mixed together in water (20 ml) producing a colourless solution.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances		Bond angles	
N1-Zn1	1.944(11)	N1-Zn1-N4	107.2(5)
N2-Zn1	1.957(12)	N1-Zn1-N3	111.1(4)
N3-Zn1	1.956(11)	N4-Zn1-N3	112.4(4)
N4-Zn1	1.946(11)	N1-Zn1-N2	106.7(5)
N5-Zn2	2.016(10)	N4-Zn1-N2	104.3(4)
N6-Zn2	2.169(11)	N3-Zn1-N2	114.6(4)
N7-Zn2	2.055(12)	N8-Zn2-N6	160.4(5)
N8-Zn2	2.167(11)	N7-Zn2-N9	127.7(5)
N9-Zn2	2.073(10)	N5-Zn2-N7	117.6(5)
		N5-Zn2-N9	114.4(5)
		N5-Zn2-N8	111.9(5)
		N7-Zn2-N8	82.2(5)
		N9-Zn2-N8	84.0(4)
		N5-Zn2-N6	85.5(5)
		N7-Zn2-N6	81.7(5)
		N9-Zn2-N6	97.3(4)
		N1-C1-S1	178.0(14)
		N2-C2-S2	176.9(13)
		N3-C3-S3	177.3(12)
		N4-C4-S4	178.7(11)
		C1-N1-Zn1	171.3(12)
		C2-N2-Zn1	164.0(11)
		C3-N3-Zn1	171.6(9)
		C4-N4-Zn1	168.6(10)

The former was added dropwise to the latter that results in a clear colourless solution. This was filtered and kept in open air for evaporation. After a few days colourless crystals of **1** suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained that were collected by filtration, washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.387 g (70%) (Found : C, 25.9; H, 4.1; N, 22.7. Calcd. for C₁₂H₂₃N₉S₄Zn₂ (**1**) : C, 26.1; H, 4.2; N, 22.8%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(N-H) 3292, 3241; ν(C-H) 2969, 2920; ν(NCS) 2098, 2085; ν(C-S) 743; UV-Vis (MeCN, λ/nm) : 271; Λ_M (MeCN, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 95.

X-Ray crystallography :

Suitable single crystal of **1** was mounted on a thin glass fiber and X-ray structural data were collected on a Bruker Smart-CCD diffractometer at 293(2) K using graphite monochromated Mo Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). The program SAINT²³ was used for integration of diffraction profiles and empirical absorption corrections were

made with SADABS²⁴ program. The best single crystal of **1** selected for data collection gave diffuse diffraction spots were overlapping and the integration of these spots could not be carried out properly by the processing software. Consequently, a small portion of the reflections collected was rejected and the structure was refined using the available data (2.07° ≤ θ ≤ 20.30°), which was adequate to give a precise structure. The structure was solved by SIR 92²⁵ and refined by full matrix least squares method using SHELXL 97²⁶. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All hydrogen atoms were located by Fourier analysis. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL 97, SHELXS 97²⁶ and PLATON 99²⁷. Crystal data and structure refinement parameters for **1** are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1**

Formula	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ N ₉ S ₄ Zn ₂
Formula weight	552.45
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	P2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁
<i>a</i> (Å)	11.2495(13)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.2840(15)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.420(2)
β°	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2269.1(5)
λ (Å)	0.71073
ρ _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.617
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)
μ (mm ⁻¹)	2.499
<i>F</i> (000)	1128
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.10 × 0.08 × 0.06
θ ranges (°)	2.07 to 20.30
<i>h</i> / <i>k</i> / <i>l</i>	-10,10/-11,11/-16,16
Reflections collected	17803
Independent reflections	2196
<i>T</i> _{max} and <i>T</i> _{min}	0.9912 and 0.5998
Data/restraints/parameters	2196/0/244
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.082
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0486 and <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1229
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0578 and <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1293
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.710 and -0.400
<i>R</i> 1 = Σ <i>F</i> _o - <i>F</i> _c Σ <i>F</i> _o , <i>wR</i> 2 = [Σ <i>w</i> (<i>F</i> _o ² - <i>F</i> _c ²) ₂ /Σ <i>w</i> (<i>F</i> _o ²) ²] ^{1/2} , calcd. <i>w</i> = 1/[σ ² (<i>F</i> _o ²) + (0.0680 <i>P</i>) ² + 5.3982 <i>P</i>]; where <i>P</i> = (<i>F</i> _o ² + 2 <i>F</i> _c ²)/3.	

Supplementary material

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis (excluding structure factors) has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center No. 840250. Copies of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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